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Breaking the Political Glass Ceiling: Women’s Representation in India and South Korea

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Abstract

The political representation of women is widely accepted as one of the key benchmarks for democratic representativeness and gender equality. Despite significant progress in education, economic participation and legal rights, women are still underrepresented quantitatively in political institutions in many democratic societies. Utilising a comparative approach on the institutional mechanisms, policy frameworks, and socio-cultural context of India and South Korea, this paper will examine women’s political representation in both countries. India has been following a reservation-based strategy, especially with the 73rd and 74th Constitutional Amendment, where it has inked reserved seats for women in local governance bodies. Through these reforms, women’s grassroots level representation has increased manifold, with more than 1 million elected women representatives at the local bodies. The main difference is that South Korea has a quota system applied to specific cases, and this system gives a political party an incentive to nominate females as candidates. Although these quotas have helped with the gradual increase of women in the National Assembly, their overall percentage remains relatively low. The study also underscores socio-cultural constraints like patriarchal attitudes and fewer political networks and party structures that continue to restrict women’s participation in the politics of both countries. The account of the comparative analysis indicates that stronger institutional mechanism as well as social change at a broader level is necessary for improved democratic governance of gender equality.

Keywords: Representation, Gender, Politics, Quotas, Governance

1. Introduction

An important indicator of both democratic inclusion and gender equality is women’s presence in political institutions. Women and men sharing equal decision-making power in the political realm is not only an issue of equity in modern democratic politics, but it also represents one of the key conditions for sound governance and social development. Despite considerable gains in educational achievement, economic participation, and full citizenship rights across much of the world, women remain underrepresented in political institutions. This enduring gap has frequently been summarised through the metaphor of a “glass ceiling,” which refers to the invisible structural and cultural barriers that keep women from top positions of power and leadership. Within the political domain, such a notion illustrates how women are excluded from access to legislative chambers by law, by party leadership within political parties, and by strategic capture outside these clusters.

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The underrepresentation of women in politics has received growing attention from policymakers, scholars and international organisations globally. It has often been highlighted by agencies such as the United Nations and various global participatory gender equality initiatives that sustainable development and democratic accountability can only be achieved when women are actively involved in governance. Greater representation of women in politics correlates with more inclusive policymaking, stronger focus on social welfare issues, and broader democratic legitimacy (Hessami, Z., and Da Fonseca, M. L. 2020: 63). Fostering this social progress will help remove structural inequalities in historical, cultural, and institutional contexts that constrain women's political participation in many societies.

In order to solve these challenges, a number of countries have put in place institutional mechanisms such as gender quotas and reservation policies for women's political representation. Fighting historical inequities, these measures help ensure that women are able to reach into the political systems and institutions where men have been deeply embedded for so long. Gender quotas can be legislated in a number of ways: reserved seats for women in legislative bodies, mandatory candidate quotas (for political parties), and voluntary party-based commitments to nominate women candidates. Although these policies have increased women's representation in many countries, their success varies considerably because of differences in political systems, electoral configuration and socio-cultural context.

India and South Korea provide two interesting yet contrasting cases for analysing the effectiveness of institutional mechanisms that are designed to improve women's political representation. Both countries are active democracies in Asia, reflecting complex political realities and different gender situations and cultural traditions. While they share some broad similarities, both societies with patriarchal social orders and marred by largely male-dominated political institutions, their methods for combatting gender imbalance in politics diverge rather starkly (Han, J. 1998: 54; Mukhopadhyay, C. C. 2021).

India has one of the largest systems for protecting gender rights in the world, particularly at the grass-roots level with respect to political reservation. In the early nineties, through the 73rd and 74th Constitution amendments, one-third reservation was also granted for women in all local self-government institutions or Panchayati Raj Institutions and municipal bodies (Choudhary, A. et al. 2025: 962). The reforms were intended to delegate power and facilitate the inclusion of traditionally marginalised communities, such as women, in local governance. The result of these policies has been the entry of millions of women into local political institutions spread across India, and can be counted as one of the largest experiments in gender-based political representation in the world. At the same time, discussions around expanding such reservations to state legislative assemblies and the national parliament have resurfaced nationally with the 2023 Women's Reservation Act (Uniyal, C. 2025: 23). This is a step that will go some way towards bridging the gender divide at higher reaches of people's representation in politics in India.

South Korea took an alternative approach to increasing women's participation in politics. Instead of mandatory quotas for women, South Korea depends mainly on candidate quota systems, which encourage or force political parties to nominate a specific percentage of female candidates throughout elections (Shin, K. Y. 2014: 84). For proportional representation lists, these quotas are usually emphasized and political parties will be expected to field women candidates in large numbers. The rollout of such policies fit within wider democratic reforms across the region and gender equality campaigns aimed at encouraging women to participate in public life. However, these measures have not ensured that South Korea's own National Assembly enjoys similarly high levels of female representation compared to other democracies, shining a light on the challenges faced by candidate-based quota systems.

A comparison between India and South Korea provides an illuminating example of how different institutional designs shape women's political representation. In India, the reservation-based system guarantees total representation (in a literal sense) by reserving seats for women candidates only and thereby obliterates not just barriers to entry into general politics but through the institution of absolute representation itself South Korea's candidate quota model makes it much more contingent on political parties' willingness to nominate female candidates or provide them with a competitive electoral opportunity (Lee, H., and Shin, K. Y. 2016: 350). As a result, the results of these two systems are different in terms of the scale and quality of women's political participation.

In addition to institutional frameworks, socio-cultural factors also impact women's political status in both countries. Traditional gendered roles, patriarchal norms, and limited access to political networks still constrain women's entry into politics. Ironically, women who break into political institutions may still have to contend with limits on independent authority (influence by social norms or political hierarchies). In addition, the existence of political dynasties and family-based political networks has implications for the mechanisms through which women reach political leadership.

At the same time, the growth of women lawmakers in both India and South Korea over time has started to question stereotypical notions of leadership and governance as well. Women in positions of power have shaped policy on educational reforms, healthcare distribution, welfare programs and gender equity across the global south and much more. They, we see, are also fundamental: the meaning of their presence has opened a wider public debate about larger issues, including these things that find something to point at and signal towards (a desire for) structural change to achieve gender balance in politics.

So, within this paradigm, examining women's political representation in India and South Korea is an implicit comparison of how institutional paths play out alongside cultural contexts and political structures to shape gender dynamics in politics. Simultaneously, building a comparative perspective of both the potential of reservation policies and gender quotas, but also

their limits, while contextualising them within broader barriers women face in smashing the political glass ceiling.

Hence, there is a need for this paper to analyse the institutional framework, relevant policy mechanisms and socio-cultural structure in the context of women's political representation within the India-South Korea comparative perspective. The comparison of the reservation-based model in India and the candidate quota system in South Korea attempts to analyse the extent to which these approaches have succeeded at increasing women's presence within political institutions. This analysis is valuable within the broader political equality context and calls for making specific policies in order to ensure women are effectively engaged, as well as their permanent representation in democratic governance.

2. Research Methodology

This research employs a comparative qualitative approach to explore women-centred political representation in India and South Korea. The comparative approach enables an analysis of the varying institutional, political systems, and socio-cultural contexts that shape women's involvement in politics. The paper will analyse these two countries in tandem, seeking to explain how different policy mechanisms play a role in achieving gender equality in political representation.

The paper is mostly dependent on secondary data. These are academic and grey literature sources, including but not limited to: books, peer-reviewed journal articles, government reports, parliamentary records, policy documents and reports published by international organisations that relate to gender equality in political participation. Some statistical data on women's representation in legislative bodies and local governance institutions have also been utilised to provide an empirical background to the analysis. These sources contribute toward a better understanding of both the historical evolution and today's situation of women's political inclusion in the two countries.

The paper explores important institutional mechanisms leading to women's representation, and focuses on reservation policies in India & gender quotas systems in South Korea. For India, this has been its impact as per the analysis due to reasons like the 73rd and 74th Constitutional Amendments and recent Legislative initiatives towards enhancing Women Representation in national and state legislatures. This paper examines the effectiveness of these policies, which are party candidate quota policies that provide incentives for political parties to nominate women candidates, especially in proportional representation systems.

Alongside an investigation into institutional factors, the research draws attention to socio-cultural variables that may impact on women's participation in politics; these include patriarchal values, gender stereotypes and political networks. This comparative framework enables the research to trace how these factors are mediated by political institutions and electoral systems. By doing so, the research will hope to explore with clarity the effectiveness of these approaches

in increasing women's political representation while also drawing out broader examples and barriers faced that have impacted gender equality outcomes in democratic countries.

3. History of Women's Representation in India

Women's political representation in India has a specific history intertwined with the country's wider struggle for independence, constitutional growth and democratic advances. The role of women in the Indian nationalist movement during the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries was another factor that helped lay the groundwork for political participation by women in independent India. Leaders like Sarojini Naidu, Vijayalakshmi Pandit and Aruna Asaf Ali were important figures in the freedom struggle that showed women could mobilise publicly and be political leaders. Their involvement defied conventional gender roles and added to early discussions over women's political rights.

India adopted a democratic polity after independence in 1947, replete with universal adult suffrage, i.e., equal voting rights for men and women right from day one (Ramanathan, S., and Ramanathan, R. 2017: 86). This was a landmark because both Western democracies were decades behind in fully enfranchising women. India's Constitution was enacted in 1950, and it embedded equality before the law and banned discrimination based on sex. Despite these provisions, women's political participation in formal institutions through the first few decades of independence remained poor. In the first Lok Sabha (1952), women represented only 4.4 per cent of members, with just 22 women elected from a total of 489 seats (Bansal, M. 2020: 78). Over the next several decades, women's representation increased little by little but still remained low. For instance, women held 5 per cent of seats in 1971, 7.3 per cent in 1984 and about 8 per cent in the early 90's (Bansal, M. 2020: 78). These figures were indicative of an ingrained and structural nature with respect to barriers that prevented women from entering electoral politics, such as patriarchal social norms, lack of money and limited political networks.

A significant watershed moment in the field of women's political representation in India came with decentralisation reforms initiated in the early 1990s. The 73rd and 74th Constitutional Amendment (1992–93) made it obligatory to reserve one-third of seats for women in Panchayati Raj Institutions and urban local bodies. These reforms are intended to bolster grassroots democracy and enhance the engagement of the 50% of underrepresented people in political systems. These policies resulted in the entry of millions of women into local political institutions across India.

Women now hold more than 46 per cent of seats in local governance institutions, aided by the expansion of what is known as reservation policies meant to bring underrepresented groups into government that were pushed beyond the constitutionally mandated one-third quota by many states. India now has over 1.4 million elected women representatives at the local government level, constituting one of the largest gender-specific political representation

experiments in the world. It turned the demographics of local political leadership on its head, and for many women who had never tried governance.

And despite this progress at local levels, women's leadership in national and state legislatures has remained relatively small. Women made up around 14.4 per cent of the total members in the 17th Lok Sabha (2019), with 78 women getting elected out of the 543 seats (Spary, C. 2020: 224). Though this is the largest number of women ever elected to India's parliament, it still fails to achieve gender parity.

Aware of this disparity, the government of India brought a Women's Reservation Bill in 2023 to reserve 33 per cent seats for women in the Lok Sabha and state legislative assemblies. Although the next delimitation exercise is yet to be carried out, this policy has the potential to increase women's representation in higher political institutions exponentially.

Thus, the historical trajectory of women's political representation in India shows that participation started with tokenism, but as time progressed was replaced by more systematic incorporation. Initial progress was slow, but some policy interventions, like reservation policies, built significant opportunities for women to access political institutions. But the question remains how numerical representation will translate into real political power and leadership in a wider democratic framework.

4. History of Women's Representation in South Korea

South Korea's history of political development, democratisation, and changing gender norms has shaped trends in women's political representation in the country. Women won the right to vote and stand for election in 1948, after being found to set action plans based on past experience in response to the establishment of the Republic of Korea. Yet, like many other deeply patriarchal societies, the early decades of the nation's political evolution saw of minimal participation by women in political institutions.

In the first National Assembly elections in 1948, one woman was elected to less than 1 per cent of the total seats (Lee, Y. I. 2018: 628). For several decades after that, women's presence in the legislature was minimal. Political participation in general was tightly controlled during the authoritarian period that lasted from the 1960s to the 1980s, and opportunities for women to enter politics were even more restricted. This changed in a significant way when South Korea transitioned to democracy in 1987, ushering the country into a new era of political freedoms and institution-building. Women's movements emerged that advocated for gender equality and increased representation of women in political institutions, building on the opportunities created by the process of democratisation. Women's organisations started to actively campaign for policy reforms related to greater involvement of women in public life.

One of the significant reforms in this regard was the gender quota policies. South Korea amended its election laws in 2000 to promote the nomination of women candidates by political

parties (Hermanns, H. 2006: 6). As part of the reform, the 50 per cent quota was extended to be applied in proportional representation candidate lists, and at least 30 per cent of candidates in single-member districts should also be female. These reforms were meant to rectify the gender imbalance in political representation by enhancing women's chances of being nominated by large-political parties.

The effects of these reforms have been slow and subtle. Women occupied about 5.9 per cent of seats in the 16th National Assembly (2000) (Kim, W. H. 2008: 131). In the 19th National Assembly (2012), women's representation rose to about 15.7 per cent (Kim, W. H. 2008: 131). In the 21st National Assembly (2020), women held 57 out of the 300 seats, or approximately 19 per cent of the legislature, a record in South Korea's history (Go, M. H., & Chung, Y. 2025: 1264).

While the numbers do reflect improvement, South Korea ranks low among developed democracies on women's representation in parliaments. So-called candidate quotas have increased the number of women in politics, especially in seats elected by proportional representation, although they still face difficulties being elected in more competitive single-member districts.

A number of female political heavyweights have also emerged in South Korea. The most vivid example of such role model status is the election in 2013 of Park Geun-hye, who became the nation's first female president (Hahm, S. D., and Heo, U. 2018: 650). Although her presidency ended in a contentious impeachment in 2017, her election represented a symbolic milestone for women's political leadership in South Korea.

In general, the history of women's political representation in South Korea demonstrates a slow shift driven by democratisation, electoral reforms, and increasing advocacy from Women's Movements. Gender quotas reform election laws, but systemic barriers in electoral politics and party systems have kept the pace of progress between gender parity higher than post-implementation, which is clear from findings across research studies.

5. Challenges Faced by Women in Political Representation

Their legal status alone is not enough to strengthen the political participation and representation of women, as both countries continue to have structural challenges, socio-cultural barriers, and institutional obstacles (especially local government) that make their politics indifferent at best towards gender equality.

One of the most relevant barriers is patriarchal social norms and gender ideologies. Politics in many societies is seen as a male territory, and women are expected to prioritise family affairs and motherhood. These dynamics of culture often make women reluctant to stand up in politics or lack support from both their families and communities. Both India and South Korea

are still strongly influenced by traditional cultural customs that persistently shape attitudes toward women as leaders.

Access to political networks and resources is another fundamental obstacle. Electoral politics, especially in India, need money, party muscle and social capital. And since women tend to lag men in these aspects, they are often at a disadvantage. Many of them have been dependent on male family members or political dynasties when entering politics at the local level in India. The same dynamic plays out in South Korea, where political parties tend to favour candidates with existing networks and money, putting women at a disadvantage.

Political party structures themselves may also be barriers. This is partially reflected in party leadership positions, which are still overwhelmingly male-led, and has a natural impact on candidate selection processes. In South Korea's candidate quota system, political parties follow quotas often only in proportional representation lists rather than competitive constituency seats. That means women have fewer opportunities to capture elections in the areas where real political power resides.

Women politicians are not out of the woods; they, too, deal with gender discrimination and media bias. Research suggests women politicians are more likely to be judged as harshly or harsher than men and often face scrutiny about their personal lives, looks or their family roles over their policy stances. Such biases can shape public perceptions and undermine women's chances at the polls.

A related challenge is the trend of proxy representation, especially noticeable in certain local governance institutions across India. In other instances, elected women in reservation policies suffer pressure from male relatives trying to exert political power on their behalf. Though no representative experience reflects that of all women, this example showcases the difficulties encountered in converting formal representation into true political empowerment.

Moreover, finding a balance between political duty and family responsibilities haunts many women leaders in staying in power. The nature of a political career, which often requires long working hours and frequent travel, combined with the pressure on women to balance that with household management, made it difficult for many women to ascend through the ranks in political parties.

Though the social barriers and corruption present in peak capitalist societies like India and South Korea both maintain levels of inequality, increasing the representation of women in political institutions within these countries is a key step in furthering equitable democratic governance. It's essential that we invest in further policy reforms, institutional support mechanisms, and sociocultural transformations to help women not only access political institutions but also exert a meaningful exercise of leadership and influence within them.

6. Discussion

Women make up half the population of India, but they account for only about 11% of the Indian parliament, fewer than in most other democracies. In both countries, the adoption of certain policy mechanisms has been steps in the right direction towards more equal representation; yet these then need to be coupled with a conducive social environment.

Yet India's record shows how powerful reservation policies can be at enhancing the proportion of women in politics. The 73rd and 74th Constitutional Amendment Acts have generated a huge institutional space for women at the local level of governance. The outcome of this journey is that millions of women have come out to enter Panchayati Raj Institutions and urban local bodies. Such a policy intervention increased the numerical representation of women in institutions but also contributed to gradually normalising leadership positions taken by women within publicly relevant decision-making. The rise of elected women representatives at the grassroots level shows how institutional guarantees can transform the gender balance of political institutions overnight.

But the Indian case also illustrates that representations, however numerical, can't deliver substantive political power. Structural challenges faced by women representatives include limited political experience to build on, reliance on male relatives or family members with pre-existing power and limited access to networks within decision-making processes. In some cases, this manifested as concern over whether women can use their power independently in the question of proxy representation. And yet research shows that, over time, many women leaders develop confidence, political acumen, and independence to become effective grassroots managers and agents of social change.

Another world model that is perhaps more relevant for South Korea is the adoption of candidate quota systems for women, instead of reserved seats. Changes in quota policies that began in the early 2000s have motivated political parties to put more female candidates on proportional representation lists. This was reflected in a gradual increase in the proportion of women in the National Assembly, from less than 6 per cent in 2000 to just under 19 per cent by 2020. A huge increase, but still modest compared to some countries that have embraced stronger quota mechanisms. The South Korean experience underlines the importance of candidate quotas but also their limits in a system where political parties nevertheless maintain significant control over much of the electoral competition and candidacy. For example, parties may meet quota requirements only on paper, putting female candidates in less competitive electoral constituencies. This means women may have a harder time winning seats in single-member constituencies, where political influence tends to be concentrated. This implies that the success of quotas is linked not only to legal frameworks but also, quite fundamentally, to cross-party commitment and investment in gender equality.

A comparison of the two cases highlights how institutional design matters. Because they ensure a threshold number of seats, reservation systems like those that have been implemented in India at the local level tend to yield quicker and more apparent increases in women's representation. Candidate quotas have been shown to depend more on party behaviour and electoral competition, factors which can inhibit the speed of any change.

Social and cultural barriers based on patriarchal norms and gender stereotypes are prevalent in both countries on a greater scale. The political participation of women is still hampered by cultural expectations for women's roles in society, limited access to financial resources and top-down male networks. So institutional reforms cannot do it all, and we need a broader societal change for making sure that gender balance in politics is sustainable.

Policy interventions do help significantly in changing the composition of political bodies, but their effectiveness over time is contingent on how institutional mechanisms interact with practices of political parties and transformations in socio-cultural norms.

7. Conclusion

Women's political representation is a key measure of democracy and gender equality. The comparison between India and South Korea suggests that despite some commonalities in the erstwhile process of guaranteeing political rights to women, objectives among both countries had diverged them to different paths due to distinctiveness in their institutional architecture, socio-political antecedents and commitments which have governed women's empowerment.

The reservation-based model followed in India, especially via the 73rd and 74th Constitutional Amendments, has actually enhanced women's representation in the local governance space. The millions of elected women representatives at the grassroots level constitute one of the world's largest democratic experiments in gender-inclusive political participation. With the Women's Reservation Act (2023) shortly becoming law, ensuring a third of seats are reserved in the national parliament and state assemblies for women, this has the potential to alter even further the landscape of female representation in politics across India.

On the other hand, South Korea has implemented a candidate quota system that promotes female candidacy. Although this method has helped lead to a gradual increase in women's representation in the National Assembly, change has come more slowly compared to reservation-based systems. Intra-party barriers and platforms continue to disadvantage women's success in constituency elections.

This comparison of these two cases indicates that institutional mechanisms have to be strong for improving women's representation in political institutions. But policy initiatives alone will not be sufficient; there needs to be broader social and political change that includes stronger support from parties, increased access to resources and networks for female candidates, as well as gender stereotypes that stubbornly persist need to be challenged.

Thus, the final goal in encouraging women to participate more in politics isn't just about equal representation; it is much broader: bringing women's views and ideas into all levels of decision-making. The progress of gender representation in India and South Korea is ongoing, reflecting a long-standing process of institutionalisation in democratic governance; yet to achieve meaningful changes, they must further courageously adopt pro-women policies through reconciliation skills and change paradigms that defy the traditional political glass ceiling.

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